

Synthesis, IR Spectra and Chelation in Some Cu(II) Coordination Compounds with 5X-Uracils and 6X-2 Thiouracils

JUAN F. VILLA and HAROLD C. NELSON

Department of Chemistry, Herbert H. Lehman College of the City University of New York,
Bronx, New York, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 28 October 1977, accepted 14 March 1978

A new series of complex compounds between 6-substituted 2-thiouracils (substituent = H, CH₃, C₃H₇ and NH₂) and Cu(II) was prepared. IR spectroscopy was used to study the bonding characteristics of these compounds. All the 2-thiouracils were shown to act as chelates via the S at C₍₂₎ and the N₍₃₎ atoms. In a parallel study, 5-substituted uracils (substituent = 1, NO₂) were also shown to act as chelates, but via the O at C₍₂₎ and the N₍₁₎ atoms.

THERE are many experimental facts linking nucleic acids and their functioning to metal ions. Tobacco Mosaic Virus has significant quantities of Fe, Ca and Mg,^{1,2} yeast RNA contains Cu and Mg, and Vaccinia virus contains about 0.02% Cu.³ Phosphorylation requires Mg or any of Mn, Cr and Co; ATPase activity is maximal at M/ATP mole ratio of 1. Also, the processes of replication, transcription and translation are dependent on metal ions such as Mg, Zn and Cu.⁴ Recently, the anticarcinogenic activity of cis-Pt(NH₃)₂-Cl₂ has been directly linked to its chelating ability to the nucleic acid bases in DNA.⁵

In order to understand the mechanism by which metal ions intervene in the function of nucleic acids, we have undertaken the isolation and study of complex compounds formed between nucleic acid components and metal ions. In this paper we probe into the interactions between substituted uracils and thiouracils (present in some t-RNAs) and Cu(II). Our immediate interest has been to determine the usual stoichiometries and the bonding site(s) at the nucleic acid bases.

Here we report the preparation of a series of compounds between 2-thiouracil and Cu(II) of the general formula: Cu(6X-2S-uracil)₂·w(solvent) where for X = H, CH₃, C₃H₇ and NH₂ and w = 3H₂O, 2H₂O, 4H₂O and 3CH₃OH respectively. Chemical analyses are used to determine stoichiometries, and infrared spectroscopy is used to elucidate the modes and sites of interaction. In addition, a similar spectroscopy study on two previously prepared compounds, Cu(5I-uracil)₂·H₂O and Cu(5NO₂-uracil)₂·2H₂O is also presented.

Experimental

Explicit detailed directions are given for the preparation of the compounds used in the study because small changes in any of the variables in their isolation resulted in undesirable products. All starting materials were

commercially available and used without purification. The preparations of Cu(5I-uracil)₂·H₂O and Cu(5NO₂-uracil)₂·2H₂O were previously reported⁶. The chemical analyses were carried out by PCR, Inc., Florida. The infrared spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 21 spectrophotometer and the samples were studied as KBr pellets.

Cu(2S-uracil)₂·3H₂O: Twenty drops of 10% NaOH were added with swirling to 0.3024 g (2.5 m moles) of 2-thiouracil in 20 ml of water at 70° bringing the pH of the solution above 10. The base fortified solution was added in small portions (4 ml to 5 ml) of a .25 M copper(II) acetate solution (1.25 m moles) at 70° with constant stirring. Initially, a black turbid mixture developed which changed to a pea-green and finally to a yellow color (pH neutral after the final addition). The mixture was heated for ten minutes in a hot water bath, cooled to room temperature and placed in an ice-bath for 20 minutes. The mixture was gravity filtered and dried in an oven at 90°. The yellowish-brown flakes that resulted were pulverized and placed in a desiccator for three days at which time the product took on its present lime-green hue (Found: C, 26.16; H, 2.39; N, 15.00. Calcd. for CuC₈H₁₂N₄O₅S₂: C, 25.84; H, 3.25; N, 15.07%).

Cu(6CH₃-2S-uracil)₂·2H₂O: A solution of 0.0866 g of CuCl₂·2H₂O (0.5 m moles) in 10 ml of methanol was added dropwise with constant stirring to 0.1258 g (1 m mole) of 6CH₃-2S-uracil dissolved in 100 ml of methanol at 55°. A light yellow solution formed immediately and turned cloudy after the addition was complete. Heating three additional minutes yielded the light yellow precipitate. The mixture was allowed to concentrate to 50 ml, cooled to room temperature and suction filtered. The product was washed with methanol and dried in an oven at 80° (Found: C, 31.86; H, 3.50; N, 15.55. Calcd. for CuC₁₀H₁₄N₄O₄S₂: C, 31.45; H, 3.70; N, 14.67%).

$Cu(6C_3H_7-2S-uracil)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$: Three drops of 10% NaOH were added to 100 ml of an aqueous saturated solution of the ligand to raise the pH to about eight. Dropwise addition with constant stirring of 3 ml of a 0.01 M $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ solution resulted in a turbid purple mixture, pH 7. Two drops of 10% NaOH were added to the mixture raising the pH to eight yielding a light green-yellow solution. Two ml of the $CuSO_4$ solution were added followed by 2 drops 10% NaOH yielding a light, green-yellow solution as before, pH 8. An additional 1 ml of the $CuSO_4$ solution was added

which resulted in a light green mixture. Two ml more of the $CuSO_4$ solution were added, followed by 2 drops of 10% NaOH. The mixture was dark yellow at this point. Finally, 2 ml of $CuSO_4$ solution were added slowly. The mixture developed a turbid green appearance. The mixture was stirred at room temperature and after 24 hours, a faint yellow product separated out. The product was filtered, washed with water and oven dried at 90° (Found : C, 35.68 ; H, 5.81 ; N, 11.16. Calcd. for $CuC_{14}H_{26}N_4O_6S_2$: C, 35.48 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 11.82%).

Fig. 1 : The IR Spectra in the 2000-1000 cm^{-1} range for : a) $6C_3H_7, 2S-Uracil$. b) $Cu(6C_3H_7, 2S-Uracil)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, c) $5I-Uracil$ and d) $Cu(5I-Uracil)_2 \cdot H_2O$.

Cu(6NH₂-2S-uracil)₂·3CH₂OH: A solution of 0.0866 g of CuCl₂·2H₂O (.5 m moles) in 10 ml of methanol was added dropwise to 0.1446 g of 6NH₂-2S-uracil (1 mmole) dissolved in 100 ml of methanol at 55°. The mixture became milky-yellow and was allowed to concentrate to half its original volume with stirring at 55°. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the light yellow product was suction filtered, washed with methanol and oven dried at 80° (Found : C, 29.30 ; H, 3.72 ; N, 18.61. Calcd. for CuC₁₁H₂₀N₆O₅S₂ : C, 29.76 ; H, 4.54 ; N, 18.93%).

Results and Discussion

A new series of Cu(II) coordination compounds of 6X-2S-uracil was isolated with 6X=H (I), CH₃ (II), C₆H₇ (III) and NH₂ (IV). This shows that 2-thiouracil is a good Lewis base, which readily coordinates to Cu(II). In a previous report, the synthesis of Cu(5X-uracil)₂·wH₂O was given⁶, where X=I (V) and NO₂

(VI) and w=1 and 2, respectively. Again, the Cu(II)-substituted uracil interactions have been shown to be real and stable.

Samples of the IR spectra in the 1700-1100 cm⁻¹ region of compounds (III) and (V) as well as those of their free ligands are given in Figure 1. Complete tabulations of the major IR bands for all complexes in the full NaCl range are given in Tables 1-3. The assignments given in the tables were arrived at by interpolation among the IR spectra of the free uracil, 2S-uracil and 2,4-dithiouracil and by direct comparison to previous published analyses for uracil⁷ and 2,4-dithiouracil⁸. The coordination sites were determined by comparison between free and coordinated ligand.

The main area of interest is the region between 1700 cm⁻¹ and 800 cm⁻¹ where the following bands are located : ν_{C(2)O}, 1730 cm⁻¹ ; ν_{C(4)O}, 1690 cm⁻¹ ;

TABLE I—OBSERVED IR BAND FREQUENCIES AND ASSIGNMENTS FOR 2S-URACIL, Cu(2S-URACIL)₂·3H₂O, CH₃, 2S-URACIL AND Cu(CH₃, 2S-URACIL)₂·2H₂O.

Free Ligand 2S-Uracil	Complexed Ligand (I)	Assignment	Free Ligand CH ₃ , 2S-Ur.	Complexed Ligand (II)	Assignment
3470 m	3420 m	ν OH H ₂ O	3420	3420	ν OH H ₂ O
3106 s	3106 m	ν CH &	3125 s	3030 w, sh	ν CH &
2940 s, sp	2940 m	ν NH	2941 m	2890 m, bd	ν NH
1701 s	1704 s, sh	ν C(4)=O	1639 s, bd	1656 s	ν C(4)=O
1686 s	1684 s, sp	& ν C=C			& ν C=C
1623 m	1633 m	δ OH H ₂ O	—	1629 m	δ OH H ₂ O
—	1623 m, sh	ν C=C	1558 s	1558 s bd	TAB I
1558 s	1558 m	TAB I	1524 w, sh	1535 m, sh	
	1535 m			1500 w, sh	δ N(1)H
1524 w, sh	1524 w, sh	δ N(1)H	1435 m, sh	1437 m	
1449 w, sp	1437 w	ν ring	1420 m		ν ring
1416 m, sp	1416 w, sh	δ N(3)H	1381 w	1385 w	δ N(3)H
1391 vw, sp	1385 vw	δ CH in-p.	1348 m, sp	1355 w	δ CH
1238 m, sp	1272 s	TAB II	1239 w	1244 w	ν ring
	1238 w		1199 s, sp		TAB II
1211 s	1211 s		1190 s, sp	1193 m, sp	
1171 s, sp	1174 w		1186 w, sh	1186 w, sh	
1155 m	1155 w		1166 s	1166 s	
1068 w	1068 w		1040 w	1040 w, bd	
1000 w	1000 w	ν ring	958 w	956 w, bd	ν ring
909 w	909 w	ν ring	929 w	917 w	ν ring
890 w, bd	890 w, bd		870 w, bd	882 w, bd	
			838 m, bd	836 w	TAB III
835 m, sp	835 w, sp	TAB III	805 w, bd	822 w, bd	
	820 w, bd			795 vw	
758 w, bd	758 w, bd				

TABLE 2—OBSERVED IR BAND FREQUENCIES AND ASSIGNMENTS FOR $C_8H_7, 2S-Ur$, $Cu(C_8H_7, 2S-Ur) \cdot 2 \cdot 4H_2O, NH_3$, $2S-Ur$ AND $Cu(NH_3, 2S-Ur) \cdot 3CH_3OH$.

Free Ligand $C_8H_7, 2S-Ur$.	Complexed Ligand (III)	Assignment	Free Ligand $NH_3, 2S-Ur$.	Complexed Ligand (IV)	Assignment
3450 w	3450 m	ν OH H_2O	3425 w	3400 m	ν NH_3 as. & ν H_2O
3125 m, bd 2941 m	3377 w 2976 w 2890 sh	ν CH & ν NH	3335 w, sh	3335 w, sh	ν NH_3 sy.
1656 s	1656 s	ν $C(4)=O$ & ν C=C	3135 m	3106 w, bd 3049 w, bd 2907 m, bd	ν CH & ν NH
1629 m, sp	1635 sh	δ OH H_2O	2941 m	1653 s	ν $C(4)=O$ ν C=C & δ NH_3
1558 s, bd	1570 w 1541 m	TAB I	1639 s	1630 m	δ OH H_2O
1500 w, sh	1490 m	δ $N(1)H$	—	1558 m, sh 1543 s	TAB I
1445 m	1441 m	ν ring	1558 s	1500 w, sh	δ $N(1)H$
1416 w, sh	—	δ $N(2)H$	1500 w, sh	1437 m, bd	ν ring
1393 w	1385 w	δ CH in-p.	1425 m, bd	1405 w, sh	δ CH in-p.
1333 w	1340 w	ν ring	1405 w, sh	1385 w	ν ring
1279 w 1241 m 1190 s 1163 m	1272 m 1230 w, sh 1208 m, bd 1166 w	TAB II	1381 w, sp	1355 w	—
1010 w	1015 w, bd	ν ring	1348 m	1295 w	TAB II
960 w	953 w	ν ring	1299 w	1241 w, bd	—
935 w	—	—	1239 w, sp 1199 s, sp 1190 s, sp 1166 s	1185 m, bd 1166 s	ν ring
885 w 861 vw 818 m, bd 785 w	876 vw 858 vw 820 w, bd —	TAB III	1041 sh 1029 w	— —	ν ring
			958 w	945 vw	ν ring
			929 w	916 vw	TAB III
			870 w, bd 838 m 806 w, bd 789 w	864 vw 836 vw 799 vw —	

TABLE 3—OBSERVED IR BAND FREQUENCIES AND ASSIGNMENTS FOR 5I-URACIL, Cu(5I-URACIL)₂·H₂O, 5NO₂-URACIL AND Cu(5NO₂-URACIL)₂·2H₂O.

Free Ligand 5I-Uracil	Complexed Ligand (V)	Assignment	Free Ligand 5NO ₂ -Ur.	Complexed Ligand (VI)	Assignment
3311 s	3370 sh 3246 m	ν OH H ₂ O	3270 sh	3450 s	ν OH H ₂ O
3125 m	3125 w	ν NH	3160 w, sh	3160 sh	ν NH
3067 s	3030 m	ν CH in-p.	3086 s, bd	3049 m, bd	ν CH in-p.
2857 m	2841 m	ν CH out-p.	2841 m, sh	2874 m	ν CH out-p.
1748 s	1736 w, sh	ν C(2)=O	1724 s, bd	—	ν C(2)=O
1700 s	1690 s, sh	ν C(4)=O	1685 s, bd	1685 s, sp	ν C(4)=O
1650 s, bd	1640 s, bd	δ OH H ₂ O	1620 m	1600 m	ν OH H ₂ O
1608 s, sp	1603 s, sp	ν C=C in-p.	—	1567 s	ν NO as.
1506 w	—	δ N(1)H	1524 s, bd	—	δ N(1)H
1471 m, sp	1460 m	ν ring	1497 sh	1497 m	ν ring
1433 m, sp	1429 m	δ N(3)H	1453 m	1440 w, sh	δ N(3)H
1397 w	1397 w	δ CH in-p.	1412 s	1429 m, sp	ν ring
1323 m, sp	1319		1359 s	1355 m	δ CH in-p.
1214 s	1211 s	ν ring	1323 s	1323 s	ν C—NO ₂
1136 s	1131 s		1232 s, bd	1292 s, bd	ν NO sym.
1044 m	1042 m		1121 w	1199 w	ν ring
992 w	992 vw	ν, δ ring	1002 w	1019 w	ν ring
935 m	935 w		978 m, bd	1007 w	
877 w	877 w, bd		858 sh	861 w	
773 m	772 w, bd	ν, δ ring	847 s	845	
753 s, sp	753 m	δ CH	824 s, bd	—	δ NO ₂
725	725	ν, δ ring	779 w	775 w	ν, δ ring
			758 s, bd	752 w, bd	δ CH

δ N_{(1)H}, 1510 cm⁻¹; δ N_{(3)H}, 1420 cm⁻¹; ν thioacetamide I, 1560 cm⁻¹; ν thioacetamide (II), 1230 cm⁻¹ and ν thioacetamide III, 860 cm⁻¹.

The changes in the spectra are dramatic upon coordination. For compounds (I)-(IV), δ N_{(3)H} decreases in intensity or completely disappears from the spectra, pointing to N₍₃₎ coordination. The C₍₂₎S moiety, as monitored by the thioacetamide bands I, II and III, is also used for coordination since there are changes in position, intensity or both in several of these bands.

ν C_{(4)O} remains unchanged in intensity and only slightly shifted in position (combination band with ν C=C); δ N_{(1)H} also remains constant in intensity and position. This is indicative that C_{(4)O} and N₍₁₎ are not used as coordination sites. However, for compounds V and VI, ν C_{(2)O} and δ N_{(1)H} disappear from the spectra, while ν C_{(4)O} and δ N_{(3)H} remain constant, indicating that the bonding sites in these compounds is via C_{(2)=O} and N₍₁₎. The high frequency ν NH band in all of these ligands is reduced in intensity, corroborating the assignment of N₍₁₎ or N₍₃₎ coordination.

Fig. 2. : Schematic of the chelation in the two series of compounds with : a) 5X-Uracil and b) 5X, 2S-Uracil.

Therefore, a shift in the bonding sites is observed in this study from $N_{(3)}$, $C_{(2)}$ S in compounds I-IV to $N_{(1)}$, $C_{(2)}$ O in compounds V and VI. Figure 2 is a schematic of the bonding observed for these compounds. There are several implications from these results. Firstly, these nucleic acids bases act as donors towards transition metal ions. This donor property would allow them to interact with metals during the transcription and/or translation processes. Secondly, these nucleic acid bases behave as chelating agents. This shows that they can also function as the coordinating (chelating) sites at RNA by metal complexes used as anticarcinogens. And, since the $N_{(1)}$ chelating site is substituted by ribose in RNA, the chelating ability of the uracil nucleotide is expected to be smaller than that of the 2-thiouracil nucleotide.

Acknowledgement

We wish to thank the Research Foundation of the City University of New York for financial assistance under grant 10597.

References

1. H. S. LORING and R. S. WAVITZ, *Science*, 1957, 125, 646.
2. H. S. LORING, S. AL-RAWI and Y. FUJIMOTO, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1958, 233, 1415.
3. H. T. SWARTOUW, *J. Gen. Microb.*, 1964, 34, 115.
4. G. L. EICHORN, *Inorganic Biochemistry* (Elsevier Publishing Co., New York), 1975, Chapter 34.
5. M. M. MILLARD, J. P. MACQUET and T. THEOPHANIDES, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1975, 402, 166.
6. J. F. VILLA, H. C. NELSON, J. ARNOLD and D. T. BARNETT, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1974, 4, 113.
7. H. SUSI and J. S. ARD, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1971, 27A, 1549.
8. J. S. DWIVEDIE and U. AWARWALA, *Indian J. of Chem.*, 1972, 10, 652.